

A Study on Services of Accenture

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ABSTRACT

Accenture is one of the leading global management consulting, technology services and outsourcing company, headquartered at Dublin, Ireland. Pierre Nanterme is Chairman & CEO of Accenture. The word “Accenture comes from Accent on the Future”. Accenture provides services in Strategy, consulting, digital, technology and operations to solve the client’s toughest challenges. Accenture strategy services provide business strategy, technological strategy and operation strategy services. Accenture consulting services provides technology, business and management consulting. Accenture digital services provide digital marketing, analytics, and mobilities services. Accenture technology service focus on technology solutions, implementation, delivery, and research and development. Accenture operations focus on the “as-a-service” model of service delivery. It includes business process outsourcing, IT services, cloud services, managed operations, security, and infrastructure services. Accenture’s workplace can become a haven, a safe space for transgender employees. In 2018, Fortune magazine named Accenture as the world most admired Information Technology Services company. Accenture works with the slogan “High Performance Delivered”. In 2017, Accenture has taken No.37 on the list of best global brands. In this study, we discussed and analysed the major services of the top IT company Accenture by studying its services to solve the client’s problems and to face future challenges using various case study methodologies. This paper includes the company’s strength and also the weakness done by SWOT analysis.

Keywords: Accenture, Accenture-company analysis, Accenture-Case study, Accenture services.

1.INTRODUCTION

The Accenture is a Fortune Global 500 IT company and also it now becomes a global leader in consulting services. Accenture is a research and analysis company, it has been started in Dublin, Ireland, since 1st September 2009. Accenture was antecedently a business associate degreed technology consulting division of an accounting organization known as Arthur Hans Christian Andersen. In 1989, It was formally established as a separate unit as Andersen Consulting after the restructuring of the Andersen Worldwide Organization. In 1991, Andersen Consulting began its first major outsourcing assignment, which involved BP Exploration’s accounting, finance, and support functions. In 2000, Accenture fully split with

Arthur Andersen and become completely independent. On January 1, 2001, Andersen Consulting adopted its present name “Accenture” which is derived from “Accent on the future”. For the full 2018 fiscal year company’s net revenues were \$39.6 billion, compared with 2017 income, which is \$34.9 billion. There is an increase of 14 percent in U.S dollars and an increase of 10.5 percent in local currency. More than 469,000 Accenture employees are serving clients in more than 200 places in 120 countries. Accenture serves with offices and operations in more than 200 cities in 55 countries. In 2015, a company working with 150,000 employees in India, about 50,000 in the Philippines, and about 48,000 employees in the US. Accenture present clients include 95 of the Fortune Global 100 and more than three-quarters of the Fortune Global 500. A French business executive Pierre Nanterme is present Chairman and CEO of the Accenture. Accenture gives professional services to its clients in the areas of strategy, consulting, technology, digital and software. Accenture provides a safe environment for transgender employees. Accenture set a goal to achieve a gender-balanced workforce with 50 percent women and 50 percent men by 2025. Presently, Accenture has 150,000 women, approximately 40 percent of its global workforce. Accenture committed to delivering innovation. In 2016, Fortune magazine called Accenture as the “World’s most admired information technology services company”. It provides efficient services and solutions to multiple companies who are on the Fortune Global 100 and Global 500 lists. Accenture working with communications and high technology, financial services, public services, products, and resources these are the five operating units of Accenture. Accenture has five business they are Accenture strategy, Accenture consulting, Accenture Digital, Accenture Technology, Accenture operations to help it’s the clients.

2.OBJECTIVES

- To know the leadership team at Accenture.
- To analyse the services and solutions provided by the Accenture.
- To know the Accenture Partners and Alliances.
- To analyse the environmental strategy of Accenture.
- To analyse the HR strategies of Accenture.
- To find the competitors of Accenture.
- To analyse the achievements and the growth of the company.
- To analyse the company using SWOT analysis.

3.SMART PRODUCTS AND SERVICES

Accenture products are Automotive, consumer goods, pharmaceuticals, and medical products, Industrial Equipment, Retail, Transportation and Travel services. Accenture provides five services to its clients of Fortune Global 500 to face future challenges. The five business of Accenture is Accenture strategy, Accenture consulting, Accenture Digital, Accenture Technology, Accenture Operations. Accenture Strategy gives business strategy, technological strategy, and operations strategy. Accenture Strategy helps clients to accomplish specific business outcomes. Accenture strategy gives the deep bench of industry knowledge with technology. Accenture consulting gives management consulting, industry specific consulting services and functional and technology consulting services to help the world’s leading companies. Accenture digital gives the Accenture compatibilities in digital marketing, mobility and analytics to help clients from which they can provide better services to a customer. Accenture applied intelligence gives advanced analytics and Artificial

Intelligence. Accenture technology comprises two areas they are Technology Services and Technology Innovation & Ecosystem. Accenture Technology services give application services-spanning system integration and Technology Innovation & Ecosystem provides R&D activities of Accenture lab. Accenture Operations provides cloud, data centers, security, infrastructure, and business processes services to clients to transform their technology infrastructure. Accenture provides performance coaching and development planning to its clients to innovating their processes.

4.CUSTOMERS AND STAKEHOLDERS

Accenture provides Strategy, Digital, Technology, and Management consulting services its clients of Fortune Global 500. Accenture solves the challenges of client's in the fields of process, marketing, staffing, technology. Accenture extends its technology and business capabilities through a powerful alliances ecosystem of market leaders. Accenture provides specialized IT skills and New IT solutions to clients.

Some of the clients of Accenture are:

- IQB Information Technologies Inc.
- Adobe Systems
- Alibaba
- Amazon Web Services(AWS)
- Apple
- Blueprint Software Systems Inc.
- BMC Software
- CA Technologies
- Callidus Software Inc.
- Cipher Cloud Inc.
- Cisco
- Click Software
- Collibra
- Copperleaf Technologies
- Drone Deploy
- EcoSys Management LLC.
- Ferranti Computer Systems NV.
- ForgeRock
- GitHub
- Google
- Guidewire Software, Inc
- Huawei Technologies
- Hyland Software
- IBM
- JDA Software Inc.
- Microfocus
- Microsoft
- NetApp, Inc.
- Nimble
- Nokia.
- Open Legacy
- Oracle

- Pegasystems
- Red Hat
- SAP
- SAS
- SOASTA
- Stibo Systems
- Tibco
- TIA Technologies
- Veeva
- Vodafone
- Xoriant Corporation.

5.SUSTAINABILITY THROUGH GREEN STRATEGY

Climate change and environmental sustainability current challenges and opportunities for the Accenture company and its stakeholders. Accenture is committed to integrating leading environmental practices into its business strategy and operations and encourages environmental awareness and responsibility among their workers, customers, suppliers and other interested parties within the context of their business.

- Encourage environmental awareness among our staff and supply environmental learning opportunities. Develop programs to harness worker enthusiasm and provide opportunities for workers to collaborate on our journey to enhance environmental performance.
- Pursuit dioxide emissions ensuing from the company's energy usage and business travel activities and implement a continuous improvement program to scale back these emissions wherever doable. Our carbon management program includes energy potency programs, renewable energy procurement, travel management programs and the use of collaboration technology.
- Maintain international certification to ISO 14001, the international standard for Environment Management Systems, in order to enhance environmental performance and demonstrate continual improvement. In alignment with our Environmental Management System, we tend to area unit committed to the bar of pollution, considering a life cycle perspective.
- Engage with their clients to consider the environmental impact of how we deliver their work and support them in addressing their own environmental impacts. Consider environmental factors when procuring goods and services. Assess the environmental performance of their key suppliers, expecting improvement in their environmental performance. Strive to advance environmental property by serving as a collaborator, caller and thought leader.

6.HR HIRING AND TRAINING STRATEGY

- Accenture team collaborates or unites or combines with its customers spread all over the world to set up and coordinated projects to:
- Create an HR methodology that is firmly coordinated with both the business system and the human capital technique to help business results while conveying high-esteem ability and HR benefits that drive an enhanced worker and supervisor encounter.

- Design and execute an HR working model fit for conveying ability and HR benefits proficiently and adequately on a worldwide scale to help the basic needs of the business.
- Drive driving practices and operational greatness crosswise over ability and HR forms by adjusting those procedures to the HR working model and the hidden HR innovation design. A coordinated HR methodology, a worldwide HR working model, and steady procedures can change HR into a finely tuned and deft association equipped for driving new levels of business esteem.

Accenture is a pioneer and thought pioneer in the HR space. The wide-achieving research activity, "The Future of HR," has distinguished a few key attributes the HR work must create to enhance its effect on the business:

- Find intermediary new wellsprings of ability.
- Assemble a versatile and engaged culture.
- Apply science and actuality based investigation.
- Build up a learning association.
- Reclassify employments and profession ways to encourage inner and outer labourer versatility.

At last, Accenture can enhance their customer's HR capacities and their capacity to convey unsurprising, great HR administrations and at the same Accenture causes the HR associations to improve as a key cooperate with the business

7. COMPETITORS

IBM: The International Business Machines Corporation (IBM) is associate Yankee transnational innovation technology-based company headquartered in Armonk, New York, United States, with its branches spread in more than 170 nations. The organization started in 1911 because the Computing-Tabulating-Recording Company (CTR) and was renamed "Worldwide Business Machines" in 1924. IBM produces and markets PC equipment, middleware, and programming, and gives facilitating and Consulting or consultation administrations in regions going from centralized server PCs to nanotechnology. Accenture is principally a frameworks combination, Consulting and outsourcing organization. IBM Services gives a substantially more extensive scope of administrations. That is, the examination isn't exactly one type to its logical counterpart. In any case, Accenture is the nearest "peer" to IBM's Services business.

Capgemini Consulting: Capgemini is one of the top competitors of the Accenture. It is a leading IT company provides professional services to its clients. Capgemini is a multinational expert administration and business consulting company headquartered in Paris, France. Capgemini provides IT advantages and is one among the world's biggest IT consulting, outsourcing and proficient administrations organizations with more than 200,000 representatives in more than 40 countries, of whom almost 100,000 are in India. It was established in 1967 by material Kampf in an urban center, France. During 2017, it is estimated that Capgemini has produced about 12.8 million Euro currencies.

Deloitte Touche Tohmatsu Limited: Deloitte Touche Tohmatsu Limited regularly alluded or called to as Deloitte, is a UK-joined or incorporated multinational expert organization or firm. Deloitte is one among the "Huge Four" accountancy associations and also the biggest knowledgeable administrations organize on the world by financial gain and variety of pros.

Deloitte gives a review, impose, Consulting, venture chance, and monetary warning administrations with in excess of 263,900 experts all around. In the year 2017, this company has generated revenue of 38.8 billion dollars. Deloitte has about 250 clients. Deloitte focuses on working together through placed across the globe to deliver excellent services to their customers.

KPMG: KPMG is one of the leading IT company that provides services like risk, financial, & business, advisory, tax and regulatory, internal audit and corporate governance. KPMG is one of the biggest auditors in the industry. It is headquartered in the Netherlands. KPMG has about 189,000 employees and them main domains includes tax, advisory and financial audit. In the year 2017 it has generated revenue of 26.40 billion US dollars. It uses practical industry knowledge that will help customers to meet their challenges and to be open to new challenges. KPMG considered as one of the top Accenture competitors.

8.FINANCE

Net Cash from (used by) Investment Activities	-1.25B	-2.23B	-610.35M	-1.17B	-1.06B
Issuance (Purchase) of Equity Shares	-1.89B	-1.97B	-2.01B	-1.9B	-2B
Issuance (Repayment) of Debt Securities	-4.19M	-2.12M	-1.05M	-	-
Increase (Decrease) in Bank & Other Borrowings	-	-	-	-	-
Payment of Dividends & Other Cash Distributions	-1.71B	-1.57B	-1.44B	-1.35B	-1.25B
Other Cash from (used by) Financing Activities	-110.16M	-17.53M	55.89M	49.31M	89.89M
Net Cash from (used by) Financing Activities	-3.71B	-3.56B	-3.4B	-3.2B	-3.17B
Effect of Exchange Rate Changes on Cash	-133.55M	42.32M	-22.98M	-279.99M	25.16M
Net Change in Cash & Cash Equivalents	934.5M	-778.74M	544.84M	-560.53M	-710.58M
Cash & Equivalents at Beginning of Year	4.13B	4.91B	4.36B	4.92B	5.63B
Cash & Equivalents at Year End	5.06B	4.13B	4.91B	4.36B	4.92B

9. SWOT ANALYSIS

The Accenture is one of the largest leading global company. Accenture can be analysed using Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats by considering different aspects.

Strengths in the SWOT analysis of Accenture:

- World's biggest consulting organization: as far as the revenue it's the world's largest Consulting company which has IT and business consultancy. It has business morals and uncompromising benchmarks for managers.
- Strong Clientele: It has a large customer base with some first-class companies having Accenture as their specialists. About 90 out of the fortune top 100 companies and in excess of seventy-five percent of fortune worldwide 500 organizations have Accenture as a consulting company.
- Service Delivery Network: Accenture has worldwide company conveyance coordinate with the presence in excess of 200 urban communities, 56 nations and utilizing 390,000 enthusiastic representatives ceaselessly attempting to give ideal administration conveyance to end clients.
- Client-Driven procedures: The strong business relations and customer-driven approach initiated and maintained by Accenture causes them in making industry based, supportable incentive for their Consulting accomplices.
- Continuous change: Like Kaizen of Toyota, Accenture is continually looking towards enhancing its abilities, contracting better and more capable labour, accordingly coordinating their guarantee
- Diverse abilities: With its five working gatherings specifically interchanges, Media and innovation, budgetary administrations, wellbeing & public administrations and

item assets it has made various capacities inside its group. Committed and prepared labour for every vertical is the thing that separates Accenture from the rest.

- Expertise: With its customer base extending from social insurance to vehicle to IT benefits, Accenture has a ton of experience and the ability behind it to complete things. Thus, Accenture has turned into the "authority" or "specialists" crosswise over various ventures.

Weaknesses in the SWOT analysis of Accenture:

- Lack of coordination: Accenture has 19 specialty units cooperatively working with the customers and with each other. This prompts clashes because of the absence of inward coordination.
- Dependency on its Consulting/consulting business: Although its business is in administration Consulting, innovation, and BPO, yet the Consulting part frames the significant wellspring of income for Accenture. This can be risky for the organization over the long haul since running such a huge task requires, to the point that the firm is prepared for terrible money related days.

Opportunities in the SWOT analysis of Accenture:

- Expansion of business: By focusing on little and fair sized ventures and extending to other creating economies (Market improvement), Accenture can build its income much more.
- Acquisitions: Accenture as of late gained 'Gaspo', an investigation arrangement supplier based out of Brazil. It likewise gained Agilex advances, which is a computerized and IT administrations supplier for U.S Govt. offices. Such acquisitions can build the scientific quality of Accenture along these lines helping it in development.
- Focusing on different organizations: More spotlight on innovation and BPO, and making the income comparable to consulting, can assist the firm in penetrating the market far and away superior. Likewise, this expansion will give a pad amid brutal monetary circumstances.

Threats in the SWOT analysis of Accenture:

- Competition: Tough rivalry from IT big companies like IBM, Capgemini, Infosys is the territory of worry for the organization.
- Improper and un-efficient monetary circumstances: During the subsidence time frame it was intense for the organization due to over reliability on premium customers. The vast customers were the initial ones which got influenced severely by the budgetary downturn. What's more thus the income drive to Accenture dropped gravely.

10. SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER INNOVATIONS

- Collaborate with more technology-related industries and companies.
- Eliminates projects and processes that don't work.

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- Establish the areas of strength and uncover potential issues in the organizations performance.
 - Conduct a world- class business system review of all of the business units to understand the level of improvements needed in each unit.
 - Key business processes- Understand the key business processes and how Customers will be impacted by the changes.

11.CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have discussed the main reasons for the sustainable growth of Accenture in the world market. The company business strategy is a model for other companies in this industry and teaches that every company should follow the long-term goal, planning, correct decision making at right time, maintaining good relations with employees, customers and stakeholders for prosperous growth. Further, building team coordination in a correct way, use of better technologies in production and making the right decision at right time to improve the product are essentials for a sustainable company. These points are useful for the success of the organization in the market. The Accenture business strategies are discussed as per the guidelines are given in the Company analysis case study methodology to understand its sustainable business strategy.

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